

THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE IN STUDENTS AS A DOLZARB PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article presents the scientific views of local and foreign scientists about the importance of social intelligence today and its topicality.*

Keywords: *intelligence, social intelligence, the problem of social intelligence, scientific analysis, socialization, age periods, interpersonal relations, social competence, stages of intelligence development, integrated intellectual ability.*

The educational system of general secondary schools of Uzbekistan is a pedagogical process of educating students with social competences based on the specific national character of the Uzbek people, moral rules and the educational requirements of national independence.

These scientific analyzes today put on the agenda the issue of creating a scientific basis of effective propaganda methods in a new style, which rely on the support of new innovative, optimal, information technologies for the formation of social competences of students and young people.

The growth of mental intelligence alone is not enough for the psychological maturity of students. In the formation of a specialist, each student is not only a subject capable of acquiring the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications for his field, but also a psychologically mature person who is flexible in social relations, able to feel the experiences of others, influence them, enter into relationships, adapt his behavior to others.

There are many aspects of psychological maturity that manifest themselves in different ways. A person with a high IQ may not meet the requirements in general terms or may not be socially and psychologically mature. Some laypersons can better analyze everyday life concerns and interpersonal issues than those with higher education. And it has the ability to analyze the level of education and IQ test results. It should be noted that when we tried to study the criteria of students' social intelligence by stages, a number of positive, scientific data were obtained.

Research aimed at studying and improving social intelligence in the field of social psychology was carried out by foreign scientists: G. Allport, L. L. Thurstone, G. Eysenck, P. Selov and Dj. Meyer, V. Keller.

Among the scientists of the Commonwealth of Nations, R.S. Nemov, B.G. Ananov, E.I. Stepanova studied the intellect as the main form of human activity in their scientific research and revealed its psychological features. The problem of social intelligence and its relation to professional activity have been studied by psychologists of our republic.

In the studies carried out by E.G. Gozиеv, M.G. Davletshin, B.R. Kadirov, G.B. Shoumarov, A.M. Jabbarov, the role of the individual in communication, behavior in managing educational activities, the important psychological factor of teacher-student partnership is independent factors of social intelligence aimed at ensuring the interdependence of thinking, cooperation and individual cognitive activities in establishing communication with students were studied.

So, the problem of social intelligence has been studied in psychology in several aspects, in which it can be seen that the general nature of social intelligence, the use of the term in science, and some

areas of activity have been researched only. However, it can be recognized that there is not enough scientific research on this problem.

Today, the subject of social intelligence is the subject of great interest of many researchers, and a number of scientific researches have been conducted on this problem. A person strives to have effective and positive relationships with others throughout his life and work. Today, at a time when competitiveness is required in every field, a number of problems regarding the positive implementation of interpersonal relations are highlighted. As an effective solution to this problem, it is necessary to ensure the socialization of the individual, to determine social flexibility.

"Intellect" is derived from the Latin language and means mind, perception, intelligence. Intellect refers to a person's ability to know, think, understand, think. It is close to spirituality and combines with a person's emotional feeling, cognitive ability and intelligence, mental maturity and striving for excellence.

In the "Pedagogy" encyclopedia, the concept of intellect is interpreted as follows: Intellect represents the level of people's mind, perception, intellect, and spiritual maturity; It also means the ability to acquire basic knowledge or critically analyze the existing knowledge through the methods of knowing the material gathered through imagination, perception, carefulness. Throughout the history of thought, opinions about intelligence have varied. There is a perception that the intellect is superior to the will as a product of the state of mind, as it relates to spirituality. Intellectual resource is an opportunity for people to enrich their intellectual capacity, lifestyle in various directions and forms, to open new aspects and perfect it, based on knowledge, life experience and perception, and intelligence.

All elements of general intelligence are directly involved in the emergence of social intelligence: thinking, types of thinking, analysis, synthesis, imagination, comparison, memory and its types. Views on the concept of social intelligence have a historical basis, which can be witnessed from the earliest written sources. In particular, in the holy book of Zoroastrian religion - "Avesta", one can witness a number of information revealing the essence of social intelligence. Pedagogical scientist S. Nishonova in her monographic work "Perfect Human Education" from the earliest times as criteria of human formation: mental maturity - common sense, high talent, potential; spiritual and moral elevation; physical maturity - physical education, charm education; emphasized that our ancestors attached special importance to education of refinement, and noted that in "Avesta" - it is possible to get rid of all bad feelings, evils and evils due to human work as the main idea.

The concept of social intelligence was first introduced to science in 1920 by E. Thorndike. He explained this concept as "communicating with conscious, thoughtful, rational actions in interpersonal relations." E. Thorndike considered social consciousness to be a unique cognitive ability that ensures the success of communication with people. The main task of social intelligence is to be able to anticipate actions in the process of communication.

V.N.Druzhinina, Yu.N.Emilyanova, A.L. Yujaninova, V.N.Kunitsina, E.S.Mikhailova and other researchers paid special attention to the determination of the effectiveness of social intelligence by cognitive abilities.

M.I.Bobneva believes that social intelligence should be evaluated as a special ability of a person formed in the environment of communication and social interaction. Also, the author tries to distinguish between social intelligence and general intelligence: general intellectual development is not directly related to the level of social intelligence. A high intellectual level is

necessary for a person. However, it cannot be a sufficient condition for the social development of a person. It can help social development. In addition, the owner of high intelligence can be devalued by his inappropriate behavior and behavior in the social environment.

A.L. Yujanina considers social intelligence along with practical and logical intelligence. The last two he includes within subject-object relations. It adds social intelligence to the scope of the subject. The author concluded that social intelligence is a distinct social ability seen in three dimensions:

1. Socio-perceptive abilities are a complete personality device that provides the possibility of individual adequate expression of a person. Its characteristics are transferred to mental processes and situations in the emotional sphere. It is also his accuracy in understanding his character in relation to those around him.

2. Social imagination is the ability to adequately model individual and personal characteristics of people based on external signs of a person. It is also the ability to clearly see the characteristics of future interaction, to predict the nature of human behavior in specific situations.

3. The social technique of communication is an "in action" component that is manifested in the ability to manage the situation and direct the quality of the interaction personality, to accept one's own role. It requires a communication technique and tool.

A.L. Yujaninova also touched on the relationship between general and social intelligence. As a result of many studies, A.L. Yujaninova comes to the conclusion that social intelligence does not depend on general intelligence, but its level of development affects human adaptability: the higher the social intelligence, the more flexible a person is. The importance of this side of the psyche is shown in numerous examples. This is evident when people who are distinguished by their high success in studying the phenomena of the material world are weak in the sphere of interpersonal relations. Thus, social intelligence is an integral intellectual ability that determines social adaptation and communication.

One of the main tasks of social intelligence is the formation of long-term relationships. Understanding the level and nature of the relationship is to positively influence each other and strengthen the relationship in the future. Social intelligence is important in professions in the field of "humanity" and provides an opportunity to predict the activities of pedagogues, psychologists, psychotherapists, journalists, managers, lawyers, doctors, politicians, and entrepreneurs.

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